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Research Article

**A CLINICAL STUDY OF SERUM LIPID PROFILE IN BENIGN
BREAST DISEASE IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL IN
PAKISTAN**¹Dr. Muhammad Saleem Malik, ²Dr. Asif Nawaz, ³Dr. Samia Ameer¹Shaqra General Hospital, msmalikrcs@gmail.com, ²Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar, doc.asifnawaz@gmail.com, ³Basic Health Unit Wadoor, Dera Ghazi Khan, samiaameer336@gmail.com**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Background- The basic aim of this study is to assess the relation between the women's profile of lipids and with the diseases of breast and to observe the relation between them.

Methodology- In this study 75 women were selected for the study and the age criteria of these women was 16- 35 years. In this study all the details was carefully recorded and lipid profile was done.

Result- It was found that 21.3% women had the disease of breast with increased serum lipid profile.

Conclusion- In this study it was concluded that there is strong relation between serum lipid profile and breast disease. The treatment was also diagnosed, to prevent possible future recurrences, use of anti-hyperlipidemic drugs for complete cure.

Keywords: Hyperlipidemia, Triglycerides, Serum lipid levels, Benign breast disease.

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INTRODUCTION:

There are a lot of abnormalities due to the lack of serum lipid profile, benign disease of breast include the stromal proliferations, epithelial, inflammatory lesions and abnormalities. Benign is the most occurring lesions of breast, but due to severity a lot of concerns is needed for the malignant lesions because it is the reason of breast cancer in women of western countries. But comparatively benign breast disease is most common than the malignant breast disease. There are a lot of symptoms of benign breast disease that can be detected through microscope. The basic reason behind the occurrence of benign breast disease is to intake excess of fat, take such as dairy products and meat, fat from animal products etc. have a higher chance of occurrence of benign breast disease. According to some studies to take fat in excess is related with the atypical hyperplasia and high risk of proliferation.

Excess of fat intake is related with BBD unlike excessive use of vitamin, carotenoids, vegetable, and E vitamin are related with low risk.

METHODOLOGY:

In this study 75 women were selected for the study and the age criteria of these women was 16- 35 years. In this study all the details was carefully recorded and lipid profile was done. All the patients were selected randomly and they are were passed through complete procedure of examination and investigation to diagnose the BBD named mastalgia, fibroadenosis, fibroadenoma. To diagnose the BBD is by FNAC as well as variouis clinical methods. Under aseptic precautions taking a 5ml sample of large peripheral vein to obtain the centrifugation. The parameters of serum lipid are serum triglyceride, serum triglyceride, density lipoprotein (LDL), very low density lipoprotein (VLDL).

Statistical Analysis:

In this study all the data analysis was performed in SPSS version 17.

RESULTS:

It was found that 21.3% women had the disease of breast with increased serum lipid profile. The age of the women was 16 to 35 years. Following is the table 1. showing the observation of elevated serum triglyceride level.

Table 1. Triglycerides Data.

Serum parameters	Age group (years)	Percentage of women with benign breast disease with elevated serum triglycerides	Serum triglyceride levels in mg/dl (mean±SD)
Triglycerides (40-140 mg/dl)	16-35	21.3%	10.08±18.08

Table 2. Serum cholesterol Data

Serum parameters	Age group (years)	Serum cholesterol levels in mg/dl (mean±SD)
Serum cholesterol (140-200 mg/dl)	16-35	170.35±16.98

Table 3: data for HDL.

Serum parameters	Age group (years)	HDL levels in mg/dl (mean±SD)
HDL (30-70 mg/dl)	16-35	52.51±10.23

Table 4: data for VLDL.

Serum parameters	Age group (years)	VLDL levels in mg/dl (mean±SD)
VLDL (25-40 mg/dl)	16-35	32.11±4.23

Table 5: Observed data for LDL.

Serum parameters	Age group (years)	LDL levels in mg/dl (mean±SD)
LDL (60-170 mg/dl)	16-35	115.27±27.88

DISCUSSION:

The basic aim of this study is to assess the relation between the women's profile of lipids and with the diseases of breast and to observe the relation between them. Benign is the most occurring lesions of breast, but due to severity a lot of concerns is needed for the malignant lesions because it is the reason of breast cancer in women of western countries. The basic reason behind the occurrence of benign breast disease is to intake excess of fat, take such as dairy products and meat, fat from animal products etc. have a higher chance of occurrence of benign breast disease. There are a lot of symptoms of benign breast disease that can be detected through microscope. But comparatively benign breast disease is most common than the malignant breast disease. According to some studies to take fat in excess is related with the atypical hyperplasia and high risk of proliferation. Patients giving history of carcinoma bosom, hypertension, and tuberculosis were avoided from the investigation. Every one of the patients were exposed to the

assurance of the serum lipid profile like complete cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, VLDL cholesterol, and Triglyceride. The investigation was done in three unique sorts of kindhearted bosom ailment. Complete consideration was given to quality control.

CONCLUSION:

In this examination it was inferred that there is solid connection between serum lipid profile and breast disease. The treatment was likewise analyzed, to prevent possible future recurrences, use of anti-hyperlipidemic drugs for complete cure.

REFERENCE:

1. Caleffi M, Filho DD, Borghetti K. Cryoablation of benign breast tumors: evolution of technique and technology. *Breast*. 2004;13:397–407.
2. Kelsey JL, Gammon MD. Epidemiology of breast cancer. *Epidemiol Rev* 1990;12:228–40.

3. Cole P, Mark Elwood J, Kaplan SD. Incidence rates and risk factors of benign breast neoplasms. *Am J Epidemiol.* 1978;108:112–20.
4. Hutchinson WB, Thomas DB, Hamlin WB. Risk of breast cancer in women with benign breast lesion. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 1980;65:13–20.
5. Fitzgibbons PL, Henson DE, Hutter RV. Benign breast changes and the risk for subsequent breast cancer:an update of the 1985 consensus statement. Cancer Committee of the College of American Pathologists. *ArchPathol Lab Med.* 1998;122:1053– 5.
6. Sarnelli R, Squartini F. Fibrocystic condition and “at risk” lesions in a symptomatic breasts:a morphologic study of postmenopausal women. *Clin Exp Obstet Gynecol.* 1991;18:271–9.
7. Bartow SA, Pathak DR, Black WC. Prevalence of benign, atypical and malignant breast lesions in populations at different risk for breast cancer. A forensic autopsy study. *Cancer.* 1987;60:2751–60.
8. Cook MG, Rohan TE. The patho-epidemiology of benign proliferative epithelial disorders of the female breast. *J Pathol.* 1985;146:1–15.
9. La Vecchia C, Parazzini F, Franceschi S. Risk factors for benign breast disease and their relation with breast cancer risk. Pooled information from epidemiologic studies. *Tumori.* 1958;71:167-78.
10. Donegan WL. Common benign conditions of the breast. In: Donegan WL, Spratt JS, eds. *Cancer of the Breast. Fifth Edition.* St. Louis, MO: Saunders; 2002: 67–110.
11. Shaaban AM, Sloane JP, West CS. Histopathologic types of benign breast lesions and risk of breast cancer. *Am J Surg Pathol.* 2002;26:421–30.
12. Morrow M. Pre-cancerous breast lesions: implications for breast cancer prevention trials. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* 1992;23:1071–8.
13. London SJ, Connolly JL, Schnitt SJ. A prospective study of benign breast disease and the risk of breast cancer. *JAMA.* 1992;267:941–4.
14. McDivitt RW, Stevens JA, Lee NC. Histologic types of benign breast disease and the risk for breast cancer. *Cancer.* 1992;69:1408–14.
15. Pfeifer JD, Barr RJ, Wick MR. Ectopic breast tissue and breast-like sweat Gland metaplasias: an overlapping spectrum of lesions. *J Cutan Pathol.* 1999;26:190–6.
16. Marshall MB, Moynihan JJ, Frost A. Ectopic breast cancer:case report and literature review. *Surg Oncol.* 1994;3:295–304.
17. Gonenc A, Erten D, Aslan S, Akinci M, Simsek B, Torun M. Lipid peroxidation and antioxidant status in blood and tissue of malignant breast tumor and benign breast disease. *J Int Cell Biol.* 2006;30:376-80.
18. Khanna AK, Tapadar JK, Khanna HD, Khanna S, Khanna A. Behavior of estrogen receptor, histological correlation and clinical outcome in patients with benign breast disorder. *Eur J Surg.* 2002;168:631-4.